

IMPORTANCE IN THE FORMATION OF STUDENTS' EXTREME COMPETENCE IN THE STUDY OF LABOR PROTECTION AND SAFETY

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Abstract: *Today, the development of society, the increasing complexity of production processes, and the rapid development of technologies make the issues of labor protection and safety even more relevant. Risks encountered in the production environment, emergencies, and possible malfunctions in technological processes can pose a serious threat to human life and health. Therefore, in-depth teaching of labor protection and safety rules to students in vocational educational institutions is an important pedagogical task.*

Key words: *Production, risk, extreme, competence, process, education, professional, skill, labor protection.*

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The formation of extreme competence of students studying in this area is of particular importance. Extreme competence is the ability of a student to act correctly in situations that require quick decision-making in an unexpected dangerous situation, to protect themselves and others, to be able to assess existing risks in advance, and to act in accordance with them. The formation of this competence requires not only the transfer of theoretical knowledge, but also the development of practical skills, the cultivation of a culture of responsibility and awareness.

From this point of view, the development of extreme competence in the process of teaching occupational safety and health plays an important role in ensuring the safety of students' life activities, forming a correct attitude towards production, domestic, and environmental hazard factors, and strengthening the skills of correct actions in emergency situations. This will serve to educate qualified, responsible specialists with a culture of safety in the future.

In accordance with educational standards, the subject "Labor Protection and Technical Safety" is taught as a general professional subject in the areas of vocational

education "Repair and Maintenance of Automobiles." From this it follows that this discipline is connected with its specific features, which are directly related to each specialty area.

In professional education, students use the laws of risk and safety, risk theory, indicators of labor intensity, working conditions, as well as many laws of physics, chemistry, and medicine in the educational process, the connections between phenomena are determined, and the connections between these phenomena are explained in an understandable way. In the process of practical training, students develop observation skills and thinking, and expand their technical knowledge. The learning process continuously encourages students to strive for self-improvement and achieve positive results in this regard. This contributes to the growth of his professional thinking. The development of professional thinking depends on the development of scientific thinking and creative abilities.

Scientific thinking and creative abilities arise on the basis of the conditions of social life and are realized on the basis of words, concepts, and logic, which are the product of social practice. Although the source of thinking is sensation, it goes beyond the reflection of direct sensation and allows one to acquire knowledge about such objects, properties, and relationships of the real world that a person cannot directly perceive.

The acquisition of knowledge is carried out with the help of such imaginary operations as thinking, analysis, comparison, synthesis, abstraction, generalization, and drawing conclusions. Empirical thinking, relying on direct perception, sensory images, and representations, does not go beyond their boundaries. The stage of general, essential concepts is limited to determining the formation of empirical concepts.

In theoretical thinking, the concrete perception of sensation reaches the level of identifying an essential commonality that is not given. As a result of theoretical thinking, theoretical concepts, mental models, hypotheses, and theories are formed. Theoretical thinking is a means of drawing conclusions through the method of deduction, based on general theory, it is possible to predict new phenomena and properties of bodies, form laws as a result of the theory.

Scientific thinking is thinking based more on theoretical concepts. Individuals with high logical thinking easily grasp theoretical concepts and can quickly identify the regular connections between phenomena.

Students demonstrate higher practical skills and abilities compared to theorists in performing tasks of practical management, planning, and identifying defects in equipment and technologies in the description of practical exercises. But they are lacking in theoretical knowledge. These characteristics of learners must be taken into account in the learning process. In the process of teaching the subject "Labor Protection and Technical Safety," it is very important to educate and develop practical and

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theoretical thinking in students based on theoretical conclusions and generalizations. In this case, for scientific thinking: clearly formulate the purpose of the research, develop a hypothesis based on previously performed theoretical or experimental research, develop a research methodology, determine the main stages of the research, conduct specific research in accordance with the developed methodology and plan, analyze the obtained results, formulate conclusions.

Independent work at each stage of the educational process is not required from students, but at the end of the session, the student should familiarize themselves with the structure of scientific research using the example of facts from the history of science in their independent work, reveal the logic of scientific research, and show how scientists came to certain theoretical and experimental discoveries. It is important to reveal what methods prompted scientists to engage in research, why the problem was solved at this stage of scientific development, and how this research was connected with the development of technology or economics.

This is necessary for the formation of a method of dialectical thinking in students. For example, when studying risk theory, it is necessary to discuss the process, explain how it logically occurred in it, and explain why Pascal and Fermat were engaged in solving this problem at that time (17th century).

This is the first way of developing scientific thinking, for example, involving students in explaining properties in production, such as industrial sanitation and occupational hygiene, "risk-cause-effect," "human-machine-environment," emergencies, civil defense, fire and electrical safety, safety techniques, working with ideal models.

The second way of developing scientific thinking is focused on solving educational problems, involving students in the study and practical application of the principles of operation of control and measuring instruments through laboratory and practical classes, searching for ways to solve problems, drawing up a verification plan, and developing verification methods.

The third way - through independent learning, the student develops and implements a learning plan for themselves, that is, bears personal responsibility for their educational process. By focusing more on areas of interest, they strive to acquire additional information and knowledge, their ability to analyze, compare, and draw their own conclusions increases, and they learn to plan their time and activities and set priorities. They get used to receiving information not only from the teacher but also from various sources, and when faced with difficulties, they strive to solve them through their own research.

The fourth way is to develop in students the ability to directly familiarize themselves with production processes in production practices, analyze them, and draw conclusions. In particular, in the course on occupational safety and health, for example,

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in production premises, it is necessary to know how to use the answer relay method to explain the factors influencing microclimate indicators on working conditions.

The systematic application of the considered methods in the learning process allows for the systematic formation of competent scientific thinking in students. For this, it is necessary to develop a special system of knowledge, the implementation of which requires students to draw conclusions. Training seminars demonstrate the emergence of general interest and discussion, which is one of the good forms of teamwork. Each student observes the clash of opinions, tries to clarify from their point of view, expresses an opinion, strives to substantiate and prove their opinion, supplements their thoughts, and comes to a theoretical conclusion. This can also be applied in practice in problem-solving and laboratory work.

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